

EFFECTS OF FUEL SUBSIDY REMOVAL ON HOUSEHOLDS IN ORUK ANAM LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria has sparked significant unrest, particularly in rural communities in Oruk Anam Local Government Area. The abrupt policy change has led to increased transportation costs and essential goods, straining households reliant on subsistence farming. Consequently, purchasing power has diminished, access to healthcare and education has declined, and food insecurity has risen, intensifying socio-economic disparities and lowering living standards. This study examined the impact of Fuel Subsidy Removal and Effects on Households in Rural Communities of Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, more specifically, it focused on assessing the impact on the standard of living, evaluating access to essential services such as education and healthcare, analyzing food security and nutritional status, examining implications for rural livelihoods, as well as understanding employment dynamics and income generation opportunities. Succinctly, the study utilized Karl Marx Social Conflict theory as its theoretical framework and employed a survey research design. Furthermore, the Taro Yamane sampling method was used to determine the sample size. Data collection included both primary and secondary sources, which were analyzed using chi-square statistical tool. The findings showed, amongst others, that the availability and affordability of essential goods and services in communities in Oruk Anam Local Government Area have changed since the removal of the fuel subsidy. The study recommended, amongst others, that the federal government should implement targeted social welfare programs to support low-income households and mitigate the decline in their standard of living.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy, Households, Rural Communities, Food Security, Poverty and Standard of Living.

Introduction

Nigeria is one of the largest oil producers in the world. The country is highly endowed with immeasurable mineral resources, most notably gas reserves and crude oil. Siddig and Walmsley (2019) argued that Nigeria owns 28% of Africa's oil reserve beaten by only Lybia. The country produces 2.5 million barrels per day in 2017 which accounted for around 24% of Africa's petroleum (Onwuemenyi, 2017). However, like in many developing nations,

these fortunes have not manifested into meaningful development of the people's welfare condition. Rather, the delivery of processed crude oil products like petrol and gas in the country has declined due to corruption, smuggling, bureaucratic bottlenecks, mismanagement and inefficiencies (Ibanga, 2019).

A subsidy by definition is any measure that keeps prices consumers pay for a good or produce below market level for consumer or for producers. Subsidies take different forms, these include; grants, tax reductions and exemptions or price controls. Others indirectly affect prices or costs, such as regulations that skew the market price in favor of a particular fuel, or government intervention, sponsored technology, or research and development, (Alozie 2019; Ola, 2017).

According to Eyiuche, (2016) the Federal Government operated fuel subsidy with the aim of making petroleum products available to cushion the effect of actual market prices of the product on the general populace. The Federal Government during the military era was of the opinion that the cost of production, transportation of fuel will be so much a heavy burden for the poor masses of Nigeria to bear alone and therefore decided to pay part of the total amount of fuel cost for every Nigerian in order to make the product available and affordable. This is actually what is referred to as fuel subsidy that is the government paying part of the total amount of fuel cost. The intention of cushioning the effect of actual market price of fuel product actually worked for a period of time, say from 1973-1983. On March 31st, 1986. Gen. Ibrahim Babangida increased the pump price of petrol from N 20k to N 39.5k. This was about 97.5% increment, (Ola, 2017).

However, Obasi (2020) observed that issues worsened with the advent to democracy. On June 1st, 2000 Chief Olusegun Obasanjo increased the pump price of petrol from N 20 to N 30 (50% increment). Gradually, the aim of the Military Government that introduced fuel subsidy was subdued and defeated. The benefits of fuel subsidy to the average Nigerian was short lived. The federal government under president Buhari administration claim to have spent over N1.4 trillion on fuel subsidy in the past five years. It also claimed to be paying heavily to subsidize kerosene which is imported into the country through the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). The fuel subsidy policy has also bred several unintended consequences and practices such as smuggling of petroleum products out of the country, the federal government also claimed that the fuel subsidy policy has made them unable to tackle problems of our collective infrastructure which are the roads, power, agriculture, fixing the refineries etc, (Alozie 2019). The Nigerian Federal Government in its attempt to deregulate the petroleum downstream sector totally removed fuel subsidy on 1st, January 2012. The former president, Goodluck Jonathan decided not to make any payment for subsidy in 2012 as he claimed that the N3.4billion being spent on subsidy was not worth it as it was mismanaged by corrupt government officials (Ibanga, 2019). Fuel subsidy was one of the major priorities of the Buhari administration but the information minister, Alhaji Lai Muhammed, stated that the country is 'broke' and cannot sustain the payment of fuel subsidy. This was followed by the increase in fuel prices from N86 to N145 per liter, more than 50% increase (Ibanga, 2019).

Given the antecedents that most Nigerians have not benefited from fuel subsidy, several economists view subsidies as highly corrupt, wasteful and bled money from the treasury into the private pockets of rich fuel importers. As a result of this obvious reality is the quest that prompt this research study.

Statement of the Problem

Nigerians did not embrace the new policy of fuel subsidy removal by the Federal Government. On 1st of January 2012 when President Ebele Goodluck Jonathan announced the fuel subsidy removal. Nigerians reacted negatively towards such policy. The Nigerian labour congress and government workers went on strike which made the nation (Nigeria) to lose a huge amount of money close to N100 billion.

However, the announcement of the removal of fuel subsidy by the incumbent administration of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu has drastically affected and left the nation traumatized, succinctly presenting a multifaceted challenge within the rural communities of Oruk Anam Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. This issue engenders a cascade of effects on households in these areas, manifesting in heightened economic strain, reduced purchasing power, and an overall deterioration of the standard of living.

As residents heavily rely on subsistence farming and decentralized economic activities, the increased cost of transportation and essential commodities due to the removal of fuel subsidies places an undue burden on already vulnerable households. Furthermore, this situation has the potential to exacerbate pre-existing socio-economic disparities, hinder access to education and healthcare services, and impede overall community development. The removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria, particularly within rural communities like Oruk Anam LGA, Akwa Ibom State, has far-reaching implications that permeate various sectors, ultimately affecting the standard of living of the populace. One notable sector significantly impacted by this policy shift is transportation. With increased fuel prices, transportation costs soar, posing challenges to mobility and access to essential services. In Oruk Anam LGA, where decentralized economic activities are prevalent, the rise in transportation expenses restricts market access for goods and services, hampering economic growth and exacerbating the economic strain on small businesses. Consequently, the viability of these enterprises is jeopardized, leading to potential closures and loss of livelihoods, thereby perpetuating the cycle of poverty within the community.

Moreover, the removal of fuel subsidies impinges on crucial social services, notably healthcare and education. Higher transportation costs dissuade residents from seeking timely medical care, undermining public health outcomes and increasing morbidity rates. In rural areas where healthcare facilities already face resource constraints, the additional burden of rising fuel costs further diminishes their capacity to deliver essential services. Similarly, access to education becomes a challenge as families grapple with inflated transportation expenses and the financial strain of meeting educational requirements. Consequently, children from vulnerable households are at risk of dropping out of school, perpetuating a cycle of educational inequity and hindering socio-economic advancement.

The agricultural sector, a cornerstone of rural livelihoods in Oruk Anam LGA, is also profoundly affected by the removal of fuel subsidies. Farmers rely heavily on fuel for irrigation, machinery operation, and transportation of agricultural produce. The escalating cost of fuel translates into higher input costs, diminishing agricultural productivity and income levels. Consequently, rural households experience reduced food security and heightened economic vulnerability, further exacerbating poverty and socio-economic disparities within the community. It is against this background that this study seeks to carry out a comprehensive investigation into the nuanced implications of fuel subsidy removal on the households in these rural communities of Oruk Anam LGA in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main Objective of this study is to examine Fuel Subsidy Removal and Effects on Households in Rural Communities of Oruk Anam L.G.A of Akwa Ibom State.

More specifically, the study seeks:

1. To examine the impact of fuel subsidy removal on standard of living of households in Akwa Ibom State in particular and Nigeria in general.
2. To access the effect of fuel subsidy removal on access of essential services by households of the study area.

Research Hypotheses

1. **H₀.** There is no significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and people standard of living in the State.
2. **H₀.** There is no significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to education, healthcare and transportation by households.

Review of Related Literature

Origin of fuel prices in Nigeria

The origin of fuel prices in Nigeria is a multifaceted issue that has evolved over the years due to various economic and political factors. Nigeria, despite being one of the largest producers of crude oil in Africa, has historically struggled with refining this crude oil locally. This paradox has led to a reliance on imported petroleum products to satisfy domestic demand, which is then sold at government-regulated prices. (Adeleji, 2017). The government's role in setting fuel prices began in the 1970s, with the aim of protecting consumers from the volatility of international oil prices. To achieve this, a subsidy was introduced, allowing Nigerians to purchase fuel at lower than market prices. There is no doubt that the oil resource has played the most significant role in Nigeria's economic development to the extent that under Gen. Yakubu Gowon the nation reportedly had the problem of finding what to spend its wealth on.

The oil contradiction has however brought the country to a sorry pass. It has led to decadence in the management of the nation as it has on its trail easy money amid deep-seated profligacy. This in turn resulted in abandoning the agricultural sector which was in great boom before the emergence of oil. Most significantly, the emergence of oil created the disease of corruption which, today, has become so complex and complicated that solution does not seem possible, (Afolabi, 2011). Talking about oil-induced corruption has seen oil oozing from all fingers of Nigeria, so difficult to hide. This is the case of the phenomenon of Subsidy which was introduced to manage the policy of making fuel available since the four refineries are not working to meet local needs. Instead of bringing joy to the faces of the people, the subsidy phenomenon has been about pains while a few already-rich people continued to swim in oil pool.

Attempts to stop the subsidy regime did not work out until the emergence of President Bola Tinubu who, himself, was a sworn enemy of any government in the past that wanted to remove subsidy. With the removal has entered economic pangs of grievous proportion as the idea of cheap fuel in Nigeria is gone. Nigerians will henceforth buy fuel like countries where there is no natural deposit of crude oil. And this is largely a result of government's inability to successfully run its four refineries that are presently at zero production. The fuel that runs the

nation is wholly imported, leading to increases in prices as the importation is at the mercy of international market reality of the Dollar, (Campbell, 2011). Following the phenomenal increase in the price of fuel, Nigeria was almost thrown into chaos as price rose to various levels, depending on the city. Fuel now sells for over ₦500 and over ₦600 in different states of the Federation.

At the very beginning, 56 years ago, fuel was sold at 6Kobo in Nigeria. In 1973, Gen. Yakubu Gowon increased the price of fuel from 6Kobo to 8.45K. In 1978, Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo increased from 8.45Kobo to 15.3Kobo. In 1982, President Shehu Shagari increased from 15.3 Kobo to 20kobo. In 1986 Gen Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida increased from 20Kobo to 39.5Kobo, and again in 1988, he increased to 42Kobo, later from 42Kobo to 68Kobo, and thereafter he increased again in 1991 to 70Kobo. Ernest Shonekan spent 82 days in power but increased the pump price from 70kobo to ₦5.00. In 1993, Gen. Sani Abacha brought down the price from ₦5 to ₦3.25k, and later increased to ₦15. There was a mass outcry in 1994, forcing him to drop the price to ₦11. But in 1998, Gen. Abdulsalam Abubakar moved the price from ₦11 to ₦25. Later in 1999, he dropped the price to ₦20. In 2002 President Obasanjo increased from ₦20 to ₦50 but decreased later the same year to ₦22, Afolabi (2023).

In 2002, Obasanjo increased again to ₦26. Another one took place in 2003 when he increased to ₦42. Still, in 2004, Obasanjo moved the price up again to ₦65. Interestingly in 2007 he increased again to ₦75. In 2007, President Umaru Musa Yar'Adua reduced from Obasanjo's ₦75 to ₦65. President Goodluck Jonathan increased to ₦141, but later reduced to ₦97. Jonathan's increase met with stiff resistance, forcing him to drop the price to ₦97. In the same year, he reduced further to ₦87. President Muhammadu Buhari who came in 2014, increased fuel price to ₦141. Later it moved to ₦165 to ₦212 in 2021. As the 2023 general elections gathered steam in 2022, fuel price rose again to about ₦500 by December 2022. Various reasons were given for the increase which was characterised by acute scarcity. The 2023 elections were held under acute fuel shortage across the country. The situation remained like that till the swearing in of the government of President Bola Tinubu. At his inauguration on May 29, 2023, the President announced to the consternation of Nigerians that subsidy on fuel had ceased, (Afolabi, 2023).

However, this subsidy became a significant financial burden on the nation's economy, with billions of naira spent annually to maintain these low prices. Attempts to remove the fuel subsidy and allow market forces to determine prices have been met with public resistance and protests, as such changes would lead to a sharp increase in fuel costs. The current official pump price is set at 515 naira per liter, but without the subsidy, prices are expected to rise significantly, which could have profound implications for a population where many live below the poverty line, (Stephen, 2015).

On another account, the history of the fuel subsidy in Nigeria dates back to April 1992 when Ibrahim Babangida government raised the price of a liter of fuel from 15.3 kobo to 20 kobo. He did it again on March 31 1986, from 20kobo to 39.5kobo, and April 10 1988, from 39.5kobo to 42kobo. On January 1, 1989, he increased the price from 42kobo to 60kobo. Although, according to Mr. Oyegoke Adeola of the Mace News, the regime said the increase in price was for private vehicles only, but the price remained 42kobo for commercial vehicles. On December 19, 1989, it moved to a uniform price of 60kobo. On March 6, 1991, the price of a liter of fuel was increased from 60kobo to 70kobo and that was the price when he stepped

aside in August 1993. Chief, Ernest Shonekan increased the price of a liter of fuel from 70kobo to N5 on November 8, 1993 but a hectic mass protest, saw Abacha take over power. The incoming Abacha regime reduced the increment to N3.25 on November 22, 1993 (Adelabu, 2012).

On October 2nd 1994, the Abacha junta increased the price of fuel to N15, from N3.25 but after massive street protests, the regime reduced the increment to N11 on October 4, 1994. That was the price till Abacha passed on and the Abdulsalami Abubakar caretaker regime raised the price from N11 to N25 on December 20 1998 and after days of sustained protests, it was forced to reduce the increment to N20 on January 6, 1999. The Obasanjo's presidency adopted fuel subsidy as the bedrock of its economic policy, for no sooner than it was sworn in than it effected an increment to N30 on June 1, 2000 but protests and mass rejection forced it to reduce the increment to N25 on June 8, 2000 and further down to N22 on June 13, 2000. The regime was again to increase the price to N26 on January 1, 2002 and again to N40 on June 23, 2003. He was to raise it up to N70 by the time he left in May 2009 but the incoming Yar'Adua regime reduced it to N65, after general protest against the new price regime.

In January 2012, President Goodluck Jonathan increased the pump price of petrol from N65 to N141 but he was forced to reduce it to N97 per litre, due to Labour strike. In January 2015, due to the fall in crude oil price in the international market, the federal government slashed the pump price of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS), otherwise known as petrol, from N97 to N87 per litre. Finally, on May 11, 2016, President Muhammadu Buhari announced that the Federal Government would no longer be paying any subsidy on oil; the price was therefore increased from N87 to N145. Thirteen years after diesel was deregulated, kerosene subsidy was removed in 2016. However, the subsidy on Petroleum Motor Spirit (PMS) has proven to be the biggest challenge to the managers of the Nigerian economy. On an annual basis, a substantial portion of the national inflow is committed to funding the subsidy scheme. Of course there are good reasons for the astronomical growth in subsidy amount - price of crude oil in the international market, volume of PMS consumed albeit debatable, and Naira devaluation are some of the drivers. In view of the significance of the amount committed to funding the subsidy regime, there is a need to have a close look at this scheme, (Adelabu, 2012).

Rationale behind the fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria

As every action has a propelling force behind, so there are reasons behind every proactive government policy. Hence, the policy of fuel subsidy removal has an underneath reasons as the government sees it as a stimulator of economic growth and development. For instance, the huge fund which is hitherto used to pay for subsidy will become available to the government for the development of the much needed infrastructure in the country, especially in the healthcare, education and transport sectors among others. If this is done, every citizen of the country will benefit. Furthermore, deregulation of the downstream oil sector will attract private sector investments, more especially foreign direct investments, to the sector. Before now investors are not attracted to the sector as they fear they may not be able to recoup their investment at government controlled prices. Foreign direct investment in the sector will create employment opportunities for the large number of unemployed Nigerians and also generate revenue to the government in the form of taxation and levies (Mboho & Udousoro, 2014).

Availability of foreign exchange with the Central Bank of Nigeria will be another result of fuel subsidy removal. A steady flow of foreign exchange to the Central bank will lead to a single foreign exchange rate regime in the country thereby stabilizing the foreign exchange market and eliminating the black market. Foreign exchange will become easily accessible for importation of goods and machineries (Umeji & Eleanyi, 2021). Removal of fuel subsidy was also seen to help removing the distortions in the market. It will bring an end to smuggling of petroleum products to neighboring countries. Due to higher price of petroleum products in the neighboring countries, fuel that are meant for domestic use in Nigeria are smuggled across border to be sold at higher prices causing scarcity in the country. The erstwhile Governor of Central Bank of Nigeria and the former Emir of Kano, Sanusi Lamido Sanusi in listing the benefits of fuel subsidy removal (Onwuamaeze & Ekeghe, 2020) said that Nigeria is the only oil exporting country that does not ripe the benefits of crude oil price rise in the international market because it fixes the price of refined products that it does not produce. So whatever it gains in high price of crude oil it losses to high price of refined products that it imports. This is so because as price of crude oil goes up the price of refined products will go up also. Therefore, removal of fuel subsidy will eliminate such revenue losses to the Nigerian government.

Socio-Economic implications of fuel subsidy removal in rural communities

According to Akintayo (2023), since the announcement of the removal of fuel subsidy by President Asiwanju Bola Ahmed Tinubu on 29 May, 2023, the aftermath of it on the citizens have been traumatizing. (Akintayo, 2023) stated that now that the price of petrol is up to N617, transportation costs, prices of food and other items have shot up tremendously, eliciting anger among rural dwellers, workers and the public at large. High cost of living has skyrocketed, for instance, transport fares have shot up by over 200 percent since subsidy removal. Prices of food items and others have all witnessed phenomenal increases. Akintayo (2023) reported that a civil servant, Omolola Ayodele, told The PUNCH correspondent that life had been unbearable for her family since May 29. “This is the worst we have experienced in like 10 years. No salary increment accompanied by the removal of fuel subsidy especially for State and Private Workers. The transportation fare across both the rural and urban areas in Nigeria has skyrocketed beyond a bearable line to especially the common man and the less privileged in the society (Akintayo, 2023).

Furthermore, in their own submissions, Mboho and Inyang (2021) highlighted and discussed the following socio-economic implications of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria:

i. Increase in poverty and vulnerability

Since the removal of fuel subsidy leads to inflation in the country, it will increase poverty in the short term (Raji, 2018). It will lead to immediate pain and hunger for families. At the individual level, the removal of fuel subsidy, and without any palliatives, could lead to fewer disposable income, fewer food in the land, and fewer medicine for sick people, and inability to afford basic education in several parts of the country especially in the Northern region of Nigeria. More families may go hungry, more children will cry in hunger and more parents will cry at their children's despair (Ozili & Obiora, 2023). The poor and middle-class consumers will witness a fall in their purchasing power, and small businesses will find their profit margins squeezed because they will face higher costs and reduced sales volumes. And if they attempt to pass on the cost to consumers, consumers might refuse to buy or they will

reduce the quantity purchased, thereby leading to low business patronage. Furthermore, the fuel subsidy removal could affect poor vulnerable groups disproportionately if there are no economic safety nets or social assistance programmes that can alleviate the economic hardship caused by the fuel subsidy removal (Ozili & Obiora, 2023).

ii. Rise in crime and criminal behavior

Another negative microeconomic implication of the removal of fuel subsidy is the potential for crime to increase (Udousoro & Mboho, 2014). The increase in the price of petrol following the removal of fuel subsidy might lead to other forms of crime such as theft of petrol from refinery warehouses, people's cars, and residential houses and from people's electric generator. The crime rate could worsen as more Nigerians struggle to make ends meet (Ozili & Obiora, 2023).

iii. Loss of job in the informal sector

The removal of fuel subsidy will lead to job loss in the informal sector that rely mostly on PMS or petrol (Houeland, 2022). The formal sector uses mostly diesel for their activities while the informal sector relies mostly on petrol. According to Ozili and Obiora (2023), the rise in petrol prices would lead to the shutdown of small businesses that cannot afford the rising cost of petrol and whose profit margins have been completely eroded by fuel subsidy removal in the formal sector.

iv. Social and cultural implications

Historically, Nigerian households have a culture of coping with pain, and this is evident in the little number of protests that have taken place in the last 10 years. Therefore, it is expected that Nigerian households would cope with the adverse price effect of the fuel subsidy removal, and their coping culture could manifest through the immediate change in consumption and spending behavior (Ozili & Obiora, 2023). It can lead to a reduction in transportation expenses as many people will avoid unnecessary movements and travels while others prefer trekking to some places within their reach. Households will avoid impulse purchases as a coping strategy, while some will avoid luxury purchases and unnecessary social gatherings that require the spending of money. This can also reflect in adjustments in burial rites and marital ceremonies of some cultures to cut down expenses. These cultural practices and societal norms could influence people's reactions to the policy change (Mboho, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

Social Conflict Theory

The conflict theory was propounded by a sociologist called Karl Marx (1818-1883). The theory sees the social world as one filled with strife and tension. Class struggle is the center point of this theory as Marx reiterated that there are two classes facing each other in every society and these two classes compete for limited resources (power, wealth and prestige). The theory argues that conflict arises when status, power and resources are not evenly distributed among members of the society and that this conflict of interest leads inevitably to social change. Power in this context is defined as the control of societal institutions, accumulated wealth, and material resources (Crossman, 2017). Thus, power and domination maintain social order in the society rather than consensus and conformity as believed by the functionalists (Investopedia.com, 2018). Some individuals in the society hold more money,

power, prestiges as well as other valuables than the others do and as such there is bound to be conflict of interest between the upper class and the lower class. Those in the upper class try to retain the resources they have in their possession through domination, oppression and exploitation while those in the lower class who do not have these resources try as much as possible to secure them by any means which will eventually lead to conflict.

In summary, according to Dahrendorf (2007), the following are the assumptions of social conflict theory:

- 1. Competition:** Conflict arises from individuals or groups that have differing interests or struggle for limited resources in the society.
- 2. Domination and exploitation:** This struggle leads to some individuals or groups dominating, exploiting and oppressing others.
- 3. Structural Inequality:** Dominant individuals and groups influence allocation of resources and structure of the society in an unequal way.
- 4. Social change:** This domination of the lower class by the upper class will inevitably lead to social change in the society where the have-nots will want to fight for their rights.

Application of the theory to the study

This study adopted the social conflict theory. The conflict theory argues that groups in the Nigerian society compete for certain resource which in this case is the fuel. Competition for fuel between the upper class (politicians) and the lower class (the masses) causes conflict between the two groups. The upper class wants to maintain their influence over fuel distribution through domination and oppression while those in the lower class want to secure fuel for running their businesses and other activities. This has led to social inequality in the Nigerian society where there is a glaring gap between the rich and the poor. The state of rural areas in the country compared to that of the urban areas is a very good example of this inequality. The bourgeoisies as termed by Karl Marx who make up the upper class live in urban areas while the proletariat (lower class) live in rural areas.

Methodology

Orodho (2005) defined research design as the scheme, outline or plan that is used to generate answers to research problems. The design adopted in this study was survey design. The researcher chooses survey method as it is one method where a group of people are studied by collecting information from them, thus it was easier to elicit responses from respondents. Mboho (2015) defined population as a set of large number of objects or the total number of conceivable observations of any kind or possessing some common specified characteristics. The population of interest in this study is the population of the Oruk Anam Local Government Area. Statistics published by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) shows that the projected population of Oruk Anam Local Government Area stands at two hundred and nineteen thousand three hundred (219,300), (Nigerianstat.gov.ng).

The sample size for this study was four hundred (400). Stratified sampling method was used as a sampling technique of the study so as to select respondents from six villages in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, including; Ikot Obio Nsu, Obio Akpa Aya, Ikot Adia, Ikot Udo Idem, Ikot Oku Usung, and Obio Ata Essien, which was calculated using Taro Yamane's sample size formula.

The questionnaires and interviews were the primary instruments for data collection. The

questionnaire was structured into two distinct sections: the first section gathered personal bio-data from the respondents, providing a demographic context for the analysis; the second section delved into questions directly related to the research topic, aiming to uncover insights pertinent to the study's objectives. In analyzing the data, simple percentage was used and chi-square to test the research hypotheses.

Hypotheses One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and people standard of living in the Oruk Anam Local Government Area.

Chi-Square Distribution Table

Cell	fo	fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$
A	98	109.8	-11.8	139.24	1.27
B	28	51.4	- 23.4	547.56	10.65
C	47	39.9	7.1	50.41	1.26
D	11	17.1	- 6.1	37.21	2.18
E	94	82.4	11.6	134.56	1.63
F	70	38.6	31.4	985.96	25.54
G	23	30.1	- 7.1	50.41	1.67
H	19	12.9	6.1	37.22	2.89
					$\sum x^2 = 47.09$

egree of freedom = (R-1) (C-1)
 = (2-1) (4-1)
 = 1x3
 = 3

The level of significance = 0.05
 Calculated value = 47.09
 Critical table value = 7.8

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 47.09 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8 the null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and people standard of living in Oruk Anam L.G.A.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to education, healthcare and transportation by households in Oruk Anam L.G.A

Chi-Square Distribution Table

Cell	fo	fe	fo - fe	(fo - fe) ²	$\frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$
A	75	86.51	- 11.51	132.48	1.53
B	72	64.08	7.92	62.73	0.98
C	45	34.71	10.29	105.88	3.05
D	20	18.69	1.31	1.72	0.09
E	87	75.49	11.51	132.48	1.75
F	48	55.92	- 7.92	62.73	1.12
G	20	30.29	- 10.29	105.88	3.49
H	15	16.31	-1.31	1.72	0.11
					$\sum x^2 = 12.12$

Degree of freedom = (R-1) (C-1)
 = (2-1) (4-1)
 = 1x3
 = 3

The level of significance = 0.05
 Calculated value = 12.12
 Critical table value = 7.8

Decision: Since the calculated chi-square value of 12.12 is greater than the critical table value of 7.8, the null hypothesis H_0 will be rejected.

Conclusion: From the above, it is observed that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to education, healthcare and transportation by households in Oruk Anam L.G.A

Discussion on Findings

Test of hypotheses one revealed that the availability and affordability of essential goods and services in your community have changed since the removal of the fuel subsidy, thus depicting that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and people standard of living in the State. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 45% strongly agreed that there are changes in the availability and affordability of essential goods and services in the respondent(s) community since the removal of fuel subsidy. This finding is consistent with Tunde's (2024) observation that the removal of the fuel subsidy has led to a significant decrease in the availability of essential goods and services in both rural and urban areas of Nigeria.

Test of hypotheses two revealed that the quality of basic amenities, such as education, electricity, and water, has changed since the removal of the fuel subsidy, thus depicting that there is a significant relationship between fuel subsidy removal and access to education, healthcare and transportation by households. The questionnaire which was used in testing the hypothesis confirms to this as majority of respondents representing 32% agreed that there have been changes in the quality of basic amenities like education, electricity, water, since the removal of fuel subsidy. This finding is consistent with Adebayo's (2023) study, which stated

that the removal of the fuel subsidy in Nigeria has led to significant changes in the provision and quality of basic amenities for its citizens. Adebayo also warned that if this issue is not addressed, the costs could become even more substantial.

Conclusion

The removal of the fuel subsidy has had profound and multifaceted impacts on households in the rural communities of Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The study revealed that this policy change has significantly affected the standard of living, with a marked decline in the availability and affordability of essential goods and services. Additionally, access to basic amenities such as education, healthcare, and transportation has been compromised, leading to a deterioration in the quality of life for many residents. The increase in food prices following the subsidy removal has also forced households to make difficult dietary adjustments, further straining their already limited resources.

These findings underscore the critical need for government intervention to address the adverse effects of the fuel subsidy removal. Without such measures, the well-being of rural households in Oruk Anam Local Government Area and similar communities across Nigeria—will continue to deteriorate. Ensuring that these communities are supported with targeted programs and policies is essential for improving their resilience, sustaining their livelihoods, and promoting equitable access to essential services.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, it is of cognizance that the following recommendations were proffered:

1. The federal government should implement targeted social welfare programs to support low-income households and mitigate the decline in their standard of living.
2. The federal government should enhance access to essential services in rural areas by investing in healthcare, education, and transportation infrastructure.

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